

1 **Genes commonly perturbed by Atg16I1 and NOD2.**

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7 Citations

8 1. Sorbara, M.T., Ellison, L.K., Ramjeet, M., Travassos, L.H., Jones, N.L., Girardin, S.E. and Philpott,
9 D.J., 2013. The protein ATG16L1 suppresses inflammatory cytokines induced by the intracellular sensors
10 Nod1 and Nod2 in an autophagy-independent manner. *Immunity*, 39(5), pp.858-873.

11 2. Travassos, L.H., Carneiro, L.A., Ramjeet, M., Hussey, S., Kim, Y.G., Magalhães, J.G., Yuan, L.,
12 Soares, F., Chea, E., Le Bourhis, L. and Boneca, I.G., 2010. Nod1 and Nod2 direct autophagy by
13 recruiting ATG16L1 to the plasma membrane at the site of bacterial entry. *Nature immunology*, 11(1),
14 pp.55-62.